

Determination of $^{177}\text{Au}^m$ and $^{177}\text{Au}^g$ α -decay branching ratios

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The procedure for calculation of the α -decay branching ratio of $^{177}\text{Au}^{m,g}$ in the case of limited measurement time is presented. In these calculations, the release times of nuclides from the target are accounted for to correct for missed activity. For the case of $^{177}\text{Au}^{m,g}$, the branching ratios were deduced to be $b_\alpha(^{177}\text{Au}^m) = 56(8)\%$ and $b_\alpha(^{177}\text{Au}^g) = 64(5)\%$.

I. Overview

The experimental procedure, explained in detail in the main text [1], involved implanting laser-ionized and mass-separated ions of $^{177}\text{Au}^{m,g}$ at the Windmill (WM) decay station. Following 30.89 s of implantation and simultaneous decay measurement, the ISOLDE beam gate was closed, and the decay measurement continued for 5.11 s. After this, the WM wheel was rotated to introduce a fresh carbon foil for implantation and the whole cycle was repeated. Assuming all of the activity due to the α decay of $^{177}\text{Au}^{m,g}$ and their β -decay daughter ^{177}Pt was measured in this 36.00s observation window, then the α -decay branching ratios are given by:

$$b_\alpha(^{177}\text{Au}^{m,g}) = \frac{N_\alpha(^{177}\text{Au}^{m,g})}{N_\alpha(^{177}\text{Au}^{m,g}) + \frac{N_\alpha(^{177}\text{Pt})}{b_\alpha(^{177}\text{Pt})}}, \quad (1)$$

where $N_\alpha(X)$ is the number of α decays of nuclide X and $b_\alpha(^{177}\text{Pt}) = 5.7(5)\%$ is the known ^{177}Pt α -decay branching ratio [2]. However, the tabulated half-lives of ^{177}Pt ($T_{\frac{1}{2}} = 10.0$ s) and $^{177}\text{Au}^{m,g}$ ($T_{\frac{1}{2}} = 1.193$ s, 1.501 s)

[2] are comparable to the decay measurement time of 5.11 s. Accordingly, some decays of $^{177}\text{Au}^{m,g}$ and ^{177}Pt were not registered in Si1/Si2 and Eq. (1) must be modified as:

$$b_\alpha(^{177}\text{Au}^{m,g}) = \frac{\xi(^{177}\text{Au}^{m,g})N_\alpha(^{177}\text{Au}^{m,g})}{\xi(^{177}\text{Au}^{m,g})N_\alpha(^{177}\text{Au}^{m,g}) + \frac{\xi(^{177}\text{Pt})N_\alpha(^{177}\text{Pt})}{b_\alpha(^{177}\text{Pt})}}, \quad (2)$$

where $\xi(X)$ is the correction factor for the missed activity of nuclide X.

II. Spectrum cleaning

In the first step of the analysis, the total measured $^{177}\text{Au}^{m,g}$ and ^{177}Pt activities, $N_\alpha(^{177}\text{Au}^{m,g})$ and $N_\alpha(^{177}\text{Pt})$ had to be accurately determined. One major issue was a partial overlap of the 5520 keV peak of ^{177}Pt with the 5486 keV peak of a ^{241}Am calibration source mounted on the WM wheel, as shown in Fig. 7 in the main text [1]. The ^{241}Am source was seen by Si1/Si2 only when the WM wheel was in a certain position during the measurement cycle. Thus, to remove ^{241}Am activity, all data collected on such instances were discarded, which reduced the total statistics recorded. Prior to cleaning, 1.7×10^4 counts were observed in the α -energy region of 5900-6200 keV for $^{177}\text{Au}^g$, while 5.8×10^3 counts were observed for $^{177}\text{Au}^m$, as detailed in the main paper. After cleaning, these values were reduced to $N_\alpha(^{177}\text{Au}^g) = 1.2 \times 10^4$ counts and

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TABLE I: The number of α decays recorded in the cleaned spectra in the regions: 5900-6200 keV for the $^{177}\text{Au}^{\text{m,g}}$ α decays and 5480-5560 keV for the 5520 keV ^{177}Pt α decay. The four rows for $^{177}\text{Au}^{\text{g}}$ correspond to data with different proton pulse timings. The fourth and fifth columns show the correction factors for missed ^{177}Pt and $^{177}\text{Au}^{\text{m,g}}$ activity respectively. The $^{177}\text{Au}^{\text{m,g}}$ α -decay branching ratios deduced from the present data are shown in the final two rows of the table. Values from the SHIP experiment [3] are also given here for comparison.

Data set	$N_{\alpha}(^{177}\text{Au})$	$N_{\alpha}(^{177}\text{Pt}(5520))$	$\xi(^{177}\text{Pt})$	$\xi(^{177}\text{Au})$	b_{α} (This work) [%]	b_{α} (SHIP) [%]
$^{177}\text{Au}^{\text{g}}_1$	3310	86	1.55(25)	1.01	56(9)	
$^{177}\text{Au}^{\text{g}}_2$	6504	103	1.55(25)	1.01	67(8)	
$^{177}\text{Au}^{\text{g}}_3$	2064	26	1.57(25)	1.01	72(10)	
$^{177}\text{Au}^{\text{g}}_4$	231	6	1.58(25)	1.01	55(20)	
Weighted $^{177}\text{Au}^{\text{g}}$					64(5)	40(6)
$^{177}\text{Au}^{\text{m}}$	4924	128	1.52(25)	1.00	56(8)	66(10)

FIG. 1: Total α -decay singles spectra from Si1 + Si2 after removal of ^{241}Am activity. (a): Measured α decays with the lasers tuned to $^{177}\text{Au}^{\text{g}}$ hfs frequencies. (b): The same, with lasers at $^{177}\text{Au}^{\text{m}}$ hfs frequencies.

$N_{\alpha}(^{177}\text{Au}^{\text{m}}) = 4.9 \times 10^3$ counts. The resulting spectra are shown in Fig. 1.

III. Correction factors for missed activity

To calculate the correction factors, ξ , for each nuclide, the implantation and decay profiles of $^{177}\text{Au}^{\text{m,g}}$ and their β -decay daughter ^{177}Pt should be known. First, the implantation profile of $^{177}\text{Au}^{\text{m,g}}$ was simulated by using a release function, as defined in [4], at the time of each proton pulse. The release parameters were extracted from analysis of Au yields presented in a forthcoming paper [5]. Then, the $^{177}\text{Au}^{\text{m,g}}$ activities were calculated from the decay law. The half-life data used in these calculations were taken from [2]. ^{177}Pt activities were deter-

FIG. 2: (a): α -decay activity of $^{177}\text{Au}^{\text{g}}$ in Si1 + Si2 overlaid with simulated activities of $^{177}\text{Au}^{\text{g}}$ and ^{177}Pt corresponding to data subset 1. (b): The same as (a) but for $^{177}\text{Au}^{\text{m}}$. Vertical lines indicate proton pulse timings. The simulated activities have been scaled to match experimental values.

mined from the assumption that all ^{177}Pt nuclei at the WM station are produced from the β decay of the corresponding $^{177}\text{Au}^{\text{m,g}}$. See the main text [1]. The resulting simulated activities for $^{177}\text{Au}^{\text{m,g}}$ are well comparable to those measured in Si1 + Si2 up to a scaling constant, as shown in Fig. 2.

The activities of each nuclide were then integrated over time intervals of 0 – 200 s and 0 – 36 s to determine their total simulated decays, $N_{\alpha, \text{sim}}^{\infty}$ and their simulated decays occurring within the observation window, $N_{\alpha, \text{sim}}$ respectively. The ratios of these numbers of decays

define the correction factors, $\xi = \frac{N_{\alpha, sim}^{\infty}}{N_{\alpha, sim}}$. The correction factors ξ are independent of branching ratios and beam intensity, but do depend on proton pulse timings. The dependence on the release model and its parameters was found to be weak.

For the $^{177}\text{Au}^m$ simulation, correction factors of $\xi(^{177}\text{Pt}) = 1.52(25)$ and $\xi(^{177}\text{Au}^m) = 1.00$ were obtained. Due to the short $^{177}\text{Au}^m$ half-life of 1.193 s, all its α decays occurred within the 36.00 s decay measurement window to within 0.01%, and thus the uncertainty of the correction factor, $\xi(^{177}\text{Au}^m)$, is negligible.

For the $^{177}\text{Au}^g$ simulation, four correction factors were calculated corresponding to four distinct subsets of data with different proton pulse timings. The values obtained were $\xi(^{177}\text{Pt}) = 1.55(25), 1.55(25), 1.57(25), 1.58(25)$, respectively. The correction factors for $^{177}\text{Au}^g$ were $\xi(^{177}\text{Au}^g) = 1.01$ for each subset. Similarly to the case for $\xi(^{177}\text{Au}^m)$, the uncertainty on $\xi(^{177}\text{Au}^g)$ is negligible.

IV. Calculation of branching ratios

The measured number of $^{177}\text{Au}^m$ α decays, $N_{\alpha}(^{177}\text{Au}^m)$, was obtained by integrating counts in the 5900-6200 keV region of Fig. 1(b). The measured number of ^{177}Pt α decays, $N_{\alpha}(^{177}\text{Pt})$, was calculated by integrating the counts of the 5520 keV peak, then correcting for its relative intensity using the ENSDF value of $I_{\alpha}^{rel} = 0.885(7)$ [6]. The branching ratio of $b_{\alpha}(^{177}\text{Au}^m) = 56(8)\%$ was then calculated with Eq. 2.

A similar procedure was followed to calculate the $^{177}\text{Au}^g$ α -decay branching ratios, $b_{\alpha}(^{177}\text{Au}^g)$, for each subset of $^{177}\text{Au}^g$ data. A weighted mean was then taken using the maximum likelihood method, resulting in the value of $b_{\alpha}(^{177}\text{Au}^g) = 64(5)\%$. These data are summarised in Table I.

V. Discussion

The $^{177}\text{Au}^{m,g}$ α -decay branching ratios were previously deduced in the SHIP experiment as $b_{\alpha}(^{177}\text{Au}^m) = 66(10)\%$ and $b_{\alpha}(^{177}\text{Au}^g) = 40(6)\%$ [3]. The $b_{\alpha}(^{177}\text{Au}^m)$ value from the present work is in moderate agreement with that of SHIP, whereas the value for $b_{\alpha}(^{177}\text{Au}^g)$ is in disagreement. The values from the present work were used for the calculations of the reduced α -decay widths of $^{177}\text{Au}^{m,g}$, presented in the main text.

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